

Psychosocial Developmental Risk Factors for Bipolar Disorder

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Introduction

Bipolar disorder is a severe mood disorder, which is characterized by cycling between the emotional extremes, in other words, mania and major depression. Bipolar disorder can be broken down into four types: Bipolar I, Bipolar II, Cyclothymic, and Unspecified bipolar disorders. First, the most severe and pronounced form is bipolar I disorder. Bipolar I is diagnosed only when an individual has experienced a manic or hypomanic episode lasting for at least 7 days, but may also include a depressive episode. Although manic and hypomanic episodes are very different, they have very similar symptoms. Both a manic and a hypomanic episode include three or more of these symptoms: Abnormally upbeat, jumpy, or wired; Increased activity, energy, or agitation; Exaggerated sense of well-being and self-confidence (euphoria); Decreased need for sleep; Unusual talkativeness; Racing thoughts; Distractibility; Poor decision-making — for example, going on buying sprees, taking sexual risks or making foolish investments. The key difference between the two episodes is the severity. Mania is more severe than hypomania and is often more noticeable in social scenes such as work, school, and other social activities. Mania may also trigger a psychotic break (Mayo Clinic, 2022). A depressive episode can be categorized as mild, moderate, or severe depending on the number and severity of symptoms, as well as the impact on the individual's functioning as well as by the different patterns of depressive episodes such as single episode depressive disorder, recurrent depressive disorder, and bipolar disorder. During a depressive episode, possible symptoms a person may experience include a depressed mood and a loss of pleasure or interest in activities. This will often last a day, nearly every day, or even weeks (WHO, 2023).

To diagnose bipolar I disorder, the patient needs to meet the criteria for a manic episode – Symptoms must be within a certain time frame = altered mood and energy most of the day almost every day for 1 week; Three additional criteria must be present to a certain extent, reflecting difference from an individual's baseline/typical behavior; and severity that it taking over one's life to a certain extent - negatively impacting the individual in work or social life, necessitate hospitalization, put self or others at risk, or include psychotic features. [DSM]

The episode can not be attributed to the physiological effects of a substance or another medical condition, though these can be a risk factor (Marissa Walsh, 2023). Second, bipolar II includes depressive episodes alternating with hypomanic episodes (Wagner-Skacel et al., 2020; Nelson, 2022). Hypomania is known as a milder version of mania that typically lasts for a shorter period. People with hypomania experience high energy or activity levels and changes in mood or behavior (Cleveland Clinic, 2021). This is usually a few days, although the length of time can vary. Cyclothymic disorder is characterized by alternations between depressive and manic states for at least 2 years, with periods of normal mood lasting less than 8 weeks. Although similar to bipolar I or II disorder, cyclothymia disorder is categorized as its own disorder due to its less extreme state, its interference with one's ability to function, and its increase in one's risk of bipolar I or II disorder (Mayo Clinic, 2022). Unspecified bipolar disorder is when a person does

not meet any of the above descriptions but has had significant mood elevation (Wagner-Skacel et al., 2020; Nelson, 2022).

Existing conceptual models and epidemiology

The mean age of onset of the first manic, hypomania, or major depressive episode is approximately 18 years for bipolar I disorder (Rowland, 2018). Special considerations are necessary to detect the diagnosis in children. Since children of the same chronological age may be at different developmental stages, it is difficult to define with precision what is "normal" or "expected" at any given point. Therefore, each child should be judged according to their own baseline. Onset occurs throughout the life cycle, including possible first onsets in ones 60s or 70s (Bauer & Pfennig, 2005). The onset of manic symptoms (e.g., sexual or social disinhibition) in late-to-mid life or late life should prompt consideration of medical conditions (e.g., frontotemporal neurocognitive disorder) and substance ingestion or withdrawal (World Health Organization, 2022). More than 90% of individuals who have a single manic episode go on to have recurrent mood episodes. Approximately 60% of manic episodes occur immediately before a major depressive episode. Individuals with bipolar I disorder who have multiple (four or more) mood episodes (major depressive, manic, or hypomania) within 1 year receive the specifier "with rapid cycling" (Depression and Bipolar Support Alliance). Interestingly, however, people with bipolar disorder more often belong to higher socioeconomic strata compared with controls or the general population. Likewise, a recent study suggested that higher socioeconomic status in parents was associated with an increased risk of bipolar disorder in children. However, people in higher socio-economic standings are more likely to have the resources to get diagnosed with and receive treatment for bipolar disorder and therefore these statistics are likely skewed to have more diagnoses in these groups.

Studies show that 1 in every 8 people in the world live with a mental disorder (World Health Organization, 2022) with bipolar disorder specifically affecting roughly 8 million adults in the US and roughly 40 million people worldwide (Nierenberg et al., 2023), concluding in approximately 2% of the general population being affected by, and diagnosed with bipolar disorder (Wagner-Skacel et al., 2020). Bipolar disorder, however, is massively underdiagnosed. Researchers have found that the median age of onset for bipolar disorder is between 15 and 25 years (Nierenberg et al., 2023), and the Stanley Center specifically recorded the median age of onset as 17.5 years (Rowland & Marwaha, 2018). While the exact relationship between stressors, the environment, and genetics as risk factors of bipolar events are unclear, studies show that the earliest episodes and triggers of bipolar disorder are often centered around psychosocial stress such as the loss of a relationship or a major life change such as graduating from college (Berzoff et al., 1996).

Research shows that bipolar disorder is one of the main causes of disability among young people, including cognitive and functional impairment and increases in mortality (Grande et al., 2015). Prevalence rates of metabolic syndrome (37%), obesity (21%), cigarette smoking (45%),

and type 2 diabetes (14%) are higher among people with bipolar disorder with approximately 15% to 20% of people with bipolar disorder dying by suicide, contributing to the risk of early mortality. The annual suicide rate is approximately 0.9% among individuals with bipolar disorder which is 20 to 30 times higher than in the general population (Nierenberg et al., 2023).

Suicide

Suicide is defined as death resulting from self-directed injurious behavior with the intent to die. A suicide attempt involves non-fatal, self-directed behavior with the intent to die, which may not result in injury. Suicidal ideation refers to thoughts of, consideration of, or planning for suicide. In the United States, suicide ranked as the twelfth leading cause of death overall, claiming over 45,900 lives. It was the second leading cause of death among individuals aged 10-14 and 25-34, the third among those aged 15-24, and the fourth among those aged 35-44. (National Institute of Mental Health) In 2021 alone, there were over 48,000 deaths by suicide, equating to approximately one suicide every 11 minutes. (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention) In terms of gender, suicide rates in 2020 were four times higher in males than females. (National Institute of Mental Health) By race or ethnicity, non-Hispanic American Indian or Alaska Native populations had the highest rates of suicide, followed by non-Hispanic White individuals. Other groups with elevated rates of suicide include veterans, residents of rural areas, and workers in industries such as mining and construction. Additionally, young individuals identifying as lesbian, gay, or bisexual have higher rates of suicidal thoughts and behavior compared to heterosexual peers (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention).

History

The earliest mentions of bipolar disorder in medical literature date back to ancient Greece (460-370 B.C.), to a man named Hippocrates, a physician often referred to as “the father of medicine.” He was the first to document the drastic switch between two moods, one of intense sadness and the other of extreme excitement: what we now call depression and mania. Depression and mania, however, continued to be considered separate conditions due to their opposing symptoms until the mid-19th century. During this time, around 1850, a French psychiatrist named Jean-Pierre Falret created a new and separate disorder that encompassed both disorders and the switch between them. He called it “folie circulaire,” meaning someone had a continuous cycle of depression and mania with varying intervals of time in between the two. In the 1950s, the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-I) was created by experts in a first attempt to normalize as well as categorize different mental illnesses. The DSM-I broke down mental illnesses into three categories: manic, depressed, and other. What we now know as bipolar disorder, due to its varying states, was classified under “other.” Bipolar disorder was not given its name and classification until the third edition of the DSM in 1980 where it was also the first defined mood disorder and bipolar disorder (Nelson, 2022).

Current paper

While classic ecological theories include chronobiology, environment, social environment, and vulnerabilities, the current review focuses on Psychosocial Developmental Risk Factors for bipolar disorder. Psychiatric research has predominantly focused on medical and genetic risk factors, however, recent research shows that psychosocial risk factors hold equal weight to this. Although the biological factors are still essential to understanding the disorder and the risk factors, this lit review focuses on psychosocial factors. Specifically, the paper will narrow in on and review research examining the roles of trauma, attachment, and early substance use and address the question: what are psychosocial developmental risk factors for bipolar disorder?

Understanding the risk factors associated with bipolar disorder has several limitations. Some gaps that were presented include identifying reliable early predictors of BD, the impact of developmental factors, underlying neurobiological mechanisms, and a lack of extensive research. Firstly, reliable early predictors and preventive interventions for bipolar disorder are lacking and there is a significant need for extended research in these areas. Secondly, the impact of developmental factors on BD's onset and progression has not been researched enough and needs a deeper exploration. Third, the underlying neurobiological mechanisms of bipolar disorder are not fully understood which can interfere with the knowledge and research around it as well as the development of targeted treatments. The diversity of BD also poses challenges in research and treatments. Lastly, there is a substantial need for more comprehensive studies to explore the relationship between bipolar disorder and other medical and psychiatric conditions, as well as the influence of outside factors. These limitations emphasize the need for further and expanded research on BD to advance our understanding and management of it.

Body/General Discussion

Early trauma - what role does early trauma play in bipolar disorder

Research shows a link between early experiences of trauma and the development of mood disorders, such as bipolar disorder. Early childhood trauma refers to the traumatic experiences endured by children typically of ages 0-5. There is a common misconception that young age shields children from the impact of such events, given their different reactions and inability to articulate their feelings compared to older children. However, research indicates that young children can indeed be affected by experiences that threaten their safety or that of their caregivers. Traumatic events can stem from intentional violence like physical or sexual abuse, domestic violence, as well as natural disasters, accidents, or war. Additionally, young children may undergo traumatic stress due to painful medical procedures or the sudden loss of a parent or caregiver. This highlights the critical need for understanding and addressing trauma in early childhood to mitigate its long-term effects on development and well-being. (Dunn, Nishimi, Powers, Bradley, 2016)

Research shows that childhood trauma is a significant risk factor for the development of mental illness in both children and adults. Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs) have emerged as a framework to delineate the various forms of trauma and adversity that children and adolescents may encounter. ACEs encompass a range of experiences, including but not limited to, physical abuse, emotional neglect, parental substance abuse, and household dysfunction. It is crucial to distinguish between adversity and trauma within the ACEs framework. While adversity refers to stressful events or circumstances that can potentially disrupt healthy development, trauma specifically involves experiences that overwhelm an individual's ability to cope, leading to significant psychological distress and impairment.

In the study conducted by Júlia et al. (2023), a population-based investigation was carried out to explore the relationship between childhood trauma, resilience, and psychopathology. To examine this, they looked at the prevalence of bullying among various sociodemographic groups in the Slovak Republic. They found that 13.5% of respondents reported having experienced bullying, with the most prevalent forms being mockery based on appearance (46.7%) and social exclusion (36.5%). Higher levels of emotional and sexual abuse were significantly associated with increased psychopathology scores across various symptom types and the Global Severity Index leading to an increase in rates of bipolar disorder (Júlia et al., 2023).

Notwithstanding the growing scientific knowledge of the role that childhood trauma plays in the development of psychiatric disorders, such as bipolar disorder, early trauma, and PTSD are often overlooked and underdiagnosed, respectively, in children. Understanding this distinction between adversity and trauma is essential for correctly assessing the impact of one's childhood experiences on their mental health, especially as it shapes difficulties regulating emotion and other mood disturbances seen in bipolar disorder.

Etain et al. (2008) conducted a comprehensive literature review to explore the association between childhood trauma and bipolar disorder. The authors carried out a systematic search of relevant publications on this topic and also presented their own data. They found that childhood trauma is prevalent and severe among individuals with bipolar disorder, with reported prevalence rates ranging from 30% to 60% across various studies compared to control groups. Furthermore, specific trauma subtypes, such as emotional abuse or neglect, were consistently associated with an increased risk of suicidal behavior and earlier age at the onset of bipolar disorder symptoms. It was also revealed that childhood trauma can significantly impact clinical features of bipolar disorder, including the increased risk of suicidal behavior and earlier age of onset. Specifically, traumatic experiences during childhood may lead to greater emotional dysregulation, increased impulsivity, and heightened sensitivity to stress, all of which contribute to an elevated risk of suicidal thoughts and behaviors. Early trauma can also accelerate the onset of BD symptoms, possibly leading to an earlier age of diagnosis as well as a more severe clinical presentation. Furthermore, childhood trauma appears to influence affective functioning between episodes in individuals with bipolar disorder. Specifically, individuals with a history of childhood trauma may exhibit greater emotional dysregulation or instability. This can occur even when the

individual is not currently experiencing manic or depressive episodes. This evidence points to potential causal pathways involving alterations in neurobiological systems implicated in mood regulation. The review suggested possible links and neurodevelopmental consequences, potentially affecting brain regions and neurotransmitter systems involved in emotional processing and regulation. For instance, disruptions in the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis and alterations in brain structures like the amygdala and prefrontal cortex have been observed in individuals with a history of childhood trauma and bipolar disorder. These findings highlight a critical need for further investigation into the specific neurobiological mechanisms underlying the impact of childhood trauma on affective regulation in bipolar disorder. Understanding these mechanisms may inform targeted interventions and treatments aimed at improving outcomes for individuals with bipolar disorder who have experienced childhood trauma (Etain et al., 2008).

A systematic review by Fisher and Hosang (2010) investigated the association between childhood maltreatment and bipolar disorder. The authors conducted electronic and manual searches to identify studies reporting prevalence rates of abuse or neglect among individuals with BD and their associations with specific clinical features, such as suicidal behavior, age at onset of bipolar symptoms, severity of episodes, treatment response, and comorbid psychiatric conditions. Based on their review of 29 relevant papers, they found that while childhood maltreatment appeared more common in BD than in controls, prevalence rates varied widely. Additionally, among individuals with BD, increased suicide attempts were consistently associated with sexual or emotional abuse. These findings highlighted methodological limitations (e.g., retrospective self-report bias, heterogeneity of measures, cross-sectional design, sample size, selection bias, and a lack of control for confounding variables) in the current body of empirical literature and thus emphasized the need for more rigorous investigations into the role of early adversity in BD development and presentation (Fisher and Hosang, 2010).

Daruy-Filho, Brietzke, Lafer, and Grassi-Oliveira (2011) conducted another systematic review investigating the impact of childhood trauma on the clinical course of BD. They performed a comprehensive search across multiple databases and identified 19 relevant articles after applying inclusion and exclusion criteria. The review highlighted that childhood maltreatment was a strong predictor of worsened clinical outcomes in BD, particularly associated with early onset of the disorder, increased suicidality, and higher rates of substance abuse among BD patients. The authors found consistent evidence suggesting that childhood abuse and neglect contribute to a more severe course of BD. However, they cautioned that the conclusions should be interpreted carefully due to the cross-sectional nature of the included studies and inconsistencies in how childhood trauma was assessed and treated as an independent variable (Daruy-Filho, Brietzke, Lafer, and Grassi-Oliveira, 2011).

A case-control study by Bernstein and colleagues (2010) investigated the association between childhood trauma and susceptibility to bipolar disorder. The study population comprised 206 bipolar patients and 94 controls who completed the Childhood Trauma Questionnaire

(CTQ), a standardized self-reporting assessment tool that is designed to quantify the severity of five distinct types of childhood trauma. The researchers compared CTQ scores between the two groups and examined the prevalence of different trauma subtypes. The authors found that bipolar patients had significantly higher CTQ total scores compared to controls. This finding suggests a potential association between childhood trauma and susceptibility to bipolar disorder. This indicates that individuals with bipolar disorder may have experienced higher levels of childhood trauma, which could possibly contribute to the development or exacerbation of the disorder making it a significant risk factor. Moreover, the presence of multiple trauma experiences was more common among bipolar patients than controls (63% vs. 33%). Multiple logistic regression analysis indicated that emotional abuse was specifically associated with bipolar disorder, showing a suggestive dose effect. These findings highlight the importance of systematically assessing childhood trauma, especially emotional abuse, in the clinical management of bipolar disorder (Bernstein et al., 2010).

One retrospective cohort study by Sugaya and others (2012) investigated the association between childhood physical abuse and the risk of various DSM-IV psychiatric disorders, including bipolar disorder. The study utilized data from the National Epidemiologic Survey on Alcohol and Related Conditions (NESARC), a nationally representative survey of the adult U.S. population. Exposure to physical abuse in childhood was assessed through structured interviews. The authors found that exposure to childhood physical abuse was significantly associated with increased risks for several psychiatric disorders. Specifically, individuals exposed to childhood physical abuse had higher odds of developing mood disorders, as well as substance use disorders, psychotic disorders, and anxiety disorders, and an increased risk of suicide attempts. These findings highlight the enduring impact of childhood physical abuse on mental health outcomes into adulthood (Sugaya et al., 2012).

In another cross-sectional study investigating the prevalence and impact of childhood abuse in patients with severe mental illness, authors (date) recruited 102 individuals diagnosed with schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, or schizoaffective disorder. Social, demographic, and clinical data were collected alongside assessments using the Brief Psychotic Relative Scale and Traumatic Life Events and Distressing Event questionnaires. The study revealed that 47.5% of patients had experienced childhood abuse, and this was associated with more severe psychosis symptoms. The findings underscored the impact of childhood abuse on the clinical trajectory and outcomes of individuals with severe mental illnesses like BD (Alvarez et al., 2011).

Attachment styles - is there a relationship between attachment style and bipolar disorder

Attachment theory is a concept that dives into the dynamics of interpersonal relationships, such as the bond between a caregiver and child. Rooted in the pioneering work of John Bowlby and later refined by Mary Ainsworth, attachment theory states that early interactions with caregivers shape internal working models of self and others, influencing behavior and emotional regulation throughout life. These attachments have been observed in

three categories; secure, insecure (avoidant or anxious), or disorganized, with each style bearing implications for psychological well-being. Attachment theory emerges as a key psychosocial factor involved in the development of mental illness.

Research highlights the relevance of attachment theory and its impact on individual functioning and adaptation. Secure attachments, fostered by consistent and responsive caregiving, lay the groundwork for healthy emotional development. Conversely, insecure attachments, marked by anxiety or avoidance, often stem from adverse early experiences, contributing to maladaptive coping mechanisms and interpersonal difficulties.

An early meta-analysis (year) of around 800 infants found a strong link between childhood trauma and attachment insecurity, with 80% of traumatized infants showing attachment insecurity compared to 36% in control groups. Subsequent studies further emphasized this connection, particularly regarding attachment anxiety and bipolar disorder in adulthood. Positive parent-child relationships during adolescence were associated with greater attachment security and reduced levels of attachment anxiety and avoidance later in life. (Wrobel, et al., 2022)

In a cross-sectional study, the impact of personality structure and attachment on symptom burden in patients with BD was investigated. In this investigation, 46 individuals diagnosed with BD were recruited for assessment using the 12-item Operationalized Psychodynamic Diagnosis Structure Questionnaire, the short version of Experience in Close Relationship-revised, and the Brief Symptom Inventory-18. The study aimed to understand how personality functioning and attachment patterns influence symptom severity in BD. The results revealed positive correlations between personality difficulties, insecure attachment, and symptom load in BD patients. Specifically, lower levels of structural integration and insecure attachment styles were associated with significantly higher symptom burdens. Surprisingly, compared to the general population, participants with BD did not demonstrate significant differences in structural integration or attachment styles. These findings highlight the importance of addressing personality structure and attachment patterns in the management and treatment of BD to potentially mitigate symptom severity.

Another cross-sectional study investigated the association between attachment insecurity and unipolar and bipolar depression. They recruited 21 patients with bipolar disorder in a current depressed episode, alongside three age- and sex-matched groups: patients with major depressive disorder, those with epilepsy, and non-clinical participants. The Experience in Close Relationships questionnaire was used to evaluate adult attachment style. The authors found that patients with both bipolar and unipolar depression exhibited significantly higher levels of attachment-related avoidance compared to patients with epilepsy and non-clinical participants. Furthermore, individuals with bipolar depression displayed notably higher attachment-related anxiety scores than all other groups. Interestingly, in both psychiatric groups, attachment dimensions were not significantly associated with overall clinical severity or depression severity.

These findings align with previous research suggesting that attachment insecurity might predispose individuals to depression, bipolar depression, and bipolar disorder (Smith et al., 2023).

Empirical research shows a clear relationship between attachment insecurity and bipolar disorder. Individuals with bipolar disorder often exhibit insecure attachment styles that are characterized by anxiety and avoidance. These patterns can impact psychosocial functioning, affecting relationships and treatment adherence. For example, another study by Pearse, Bucci, Jessica, and Berry (2020) was done on the relationship between attachment and functioning for people with serious mental illness including bipolar disorder, and the relationship between adult attachment style and functioning in severe mental illness (SMI) was examined. Ten studies indicated that secure attachment correlated with better functioning, while insecure attachment, particularly anxious style, correlated with functional impairments. This underscores the importance of considering attachment in psychological interventions for individuals with SMI (Pearse, Bucci, Jessica, and Berry, 2020).

Early substance use

Early substance use refers to the consumption of drugs or alcohol at a young age, typically during adolescence or earlier. Substances may include alcohol, nicotine, and illicit drugs such as cannabis, cocaine, and amphetamines, and can have major negative consequences like stunted development and mental health issues, such as addiction and bipolar disorder. Researchers have identified a clear connection between bipolar disorder and substance use disorders. For example, studies by Cerullo and Strakowski found that SUD and bipolar disorder are likely to co-occur. Based on numerous large-scale studies, it is estimated with caution that individuals with bipolar I disorder experience a lifetime prevalence of alcohol and other drug use disorders of at least 40% (Cerullo and Strakowski, 2007). This may be due to the fact that individuals with bipolar disorder are particularly vulnerable to developing SUD. These conditions share neurobiological and genetic factors that contribute to their risks however the current review focuses on the psychosocial factors.

The coexistence of SUD and bipolar disorder has presented a major challenge in the diagnosis and treatment of both conditions. Among individuals with SUD, unpredictable fluctuations in mood have been shown to parallel those of bipolar disorder which can make it more challenging for clinicians to accurately diagnose them. Additionally, substance use may exacerbate mood instability, increase treatment resistance, and necessitate more frequent hospitalizations (Lalli, Brouillette, Kapczinski, and Cardoso, 2021).

A systematic review conducted by Cerullo and Strakowski examined the epidemiology of patients with bipolar disorder and co-occurring with SUD. They identified studies via Medline

and references, focusing on epidemiology, outcome, and treatment. Substance use disorders (SUDs) are prevalent in bipolar I and II disorders, with a lifetime prevalence of at least 40% in bipolar I patients. Alcohol and cannabis are commonly abused, followed by cocaine and opioids. Co-occurring SUDs correlate with negative outcomes including more frequent affective episodes, poor treatment compliance, lower quality of life, and increased suicidal behavior. Limited treatment research targets this population. Open-label trials suggest the potential efficacy of quetiapine, aripiprazole, and lamotrigine in treating affective and substance use symptoms in bipolar patients with cocaine dependence. Valproate, as an adjunct to lithium, improves mood and alcohol use symptoms in bipolar patients with alcohol dependence. Lithium also benefits mood and SUD symptoms in bipolar adolescents. More research, including double-blind placebo-controlled trials, is needed to establish medication efficacy. Future studies should explore treatments for bipolar disorder or SUDs in isolation and consider patients with prior SUDs in clinical trials for new bipolar medications (Cerullo and Strakowski, 2007).

One large-scale epidemiological study used the National Epidemiologic Survey on Alcohol and Related Conditions (NESARC), to investigate the prevalence and co-occurrence of substance use disorders (SUDs) in individuals with bipolar I disorder. They surveyed 43,093 respondents in the US. Among those with bipolar I disorder, the study found a high lifetime prevalence of co-occurring alcohol use disorders (58%) and any drug use disorder (38%). Regier et al. (1990) conducted another notable survey, the National Institutes of Mental Health Epidemiologic Catchment Area Program, involving 20,291 individuals from various settings to study the prevalence of mental illness and SUDs. Among individuals with bipolar I disorder, they found a lifetime history of any drug or alcohol use disorder in 61%, with specific rates of 46% for alcohol use disorder and 41% for drug abuse or dependence. For individuals with bipolar II disorder, the same study reported a lifetime history of any drug or alcohol use disorder in 48%, with rates of 39% for alcohol use disorder and 21% for drug abuse or dependence. Additionally, the authors highlighted that among various psychiatric illnesses, only antisocial personality disorder exhibited a higher lifetime prevalence rate of any SUD (84%) (Grant et al., 2005).

Similarly, a longitudinal cohort study examining comorbid substance use disorders (SUDs) in patients with bipolar I disorder who had experienced a first manic or mixed episode. The study utilized data from the McLean-Harvard First-Episode Mania Study, focusing on the initial 112 patients followed for up to two years. At the outset, 33% of patients exhibited a SUD, primarily alcohol abuse and dependence, cannabis use disorders, and cocaine-related issues. Anxiety disorders were also notably more prevalent among those with SUD (30% vs. 13%). Over the follow-up period, the prevalence of current SUDs increased to 39% among the remaining 80 patients, underscoring the persistent challenges of managing comorbidities in bipolar disorder (Baethge et al., 2005).

Smith and colleagues (2023) conducted a systematic review investigating the association between substance use and bipolar disorder (BD). They identified cannabis use, particularly at

least three times per week, as a significant risk factor for BD. This finding supports prior research suggesting a link between substance use and increased BD risk, aligning with Kenneson et al. (2013), who demonstrated elevated BD risk among individuals with substance use disorders (Lalli, Brouillette, Kapczinski, and Cardoso, 2021).

Conclusion

The current paper explored early trauma, attachment, and early substance use as contributing factors to the later development of bipolar disorder. The body of empirical literature points to early trauma, attachment, and early substance abuse being possible risk factors for bipolar disorder. The psychosocial developmental risk factors for bipolar disorder highlight the complex relationship between adverse or traumatic experiences during development, attachment insecurity, and early substance use in shaping the course and presentation of this severe mood disorder.

The first section of this paper highlighted that childhood trauma consistently emerges as a significant risk factor associated with increased susceptibility to bipolar disorder (e.g., Etain et al. (2008), Fisher and Hosang (2010), and Bernstein et al. (2010)). Early trauma has also been found to exacerbate outcomes in patients with bipolar disorder and predict increased rates of suicidality and increased rates of symptoms. The second section of this review focuses on attachment theory and how it can provide further insights into the interpersonal dynamics that contribute to vulnerability or resilience in bipolar disorder. Specifically, individuals with bipolar disorder who exhibit insecure attachment styles characterized by avoidance or anxiety tend to experience more severe symptoms and functional impairments. For example, individuals with anxious attachment styles might struggle with heightened emotional reactivity and difficulty regulating mood swings, leading to greater symptom severity and interpersonal challenges in their relationships. On the other hand, those with avoidant attachment styles may exhibit emotional detachment and difficulties in seeking or maintaining social support, which can exacerbate feelings of isolation and impair functioning in daily life. In the third section of the review, early substance use emerges as a critical risk factor for the development of bipolar disorder. Specifically, the use of substances such as alcohol, nicotine, cannabis, cocaine, and amphetamines during adolescence or earlier stages of life has been implicated in increasing vulnerability to both substance use disorders (SUDs) and bipolar disorder. Research shows that early substance use can disrupt normal brain development and functioning, particularly in regions associated with impulse control, emotion regulation, and reward processing. This disruption may create a neurobiological susceptibility to addictive behaviors and mood dysregulation characteristic of bipolar disorder. Furthermore, early substance use can interact with genetic and environmental factors to increase the risk of developing bipolar disorder. Additionally, the co-occurrence of substance use and bipolar disorder presents challenges in both diagnosis and treatment. In individuals diagnosed with bipolar I disorder, researchers identified

that 61% had experienced a lifetime history of either drug or alcohol use disorder, with specific rates of 46% for alcohol use disorder and 41% for drug abuse or dependence. For those with bipolar II disorder, the study found that 48% had a lifetime history of any drug or alcohol use disorder, including rates of 39% for alcohol use disorder and 21% for drug abuse or dependence. Furthermore, the authors noted that among different psychiatric conditions, only antisocial personality disorder showed a higher lifetime prevalence rate of any substance use disorder (84%).

Strengths and Limitations of the Literature

The reviewed studies exhibit varying strengths and limitations. Limitations of the review include a lack of sample sizes, a lack of variety in sociodemographics, and control groups differing across studies which could affect the generalizability of the findings. Furthermore, some of the studies used longitudinal designs, offering insights into temporal relationships, whereas others used cross-sectional approaches, limiting causal inferences. Finally, the reliability and validity of measures assessing trauma, attachment, and substance use vary, impacting the robustness of study outcomes.

Future research

Although this paper focuses specifically on early trauma, attachment, and early substance abuse as risk factors for bipolar disorder, future research should explore these factors in conjunction with other potential risk factors. Longitudinal studies with diverse populations and comprehensive assessments are needed to elucidate the interplay of psychosocial factors in bipolar disorder development. Further investigation into other potential risk factors should be done to expand the comprehension of bipolar disorder. Understanding the impact of childhood trauma on affective functioning underscores the critical need for trauma-informed interventions in clinical settings. Therapeutic approaches targeting emotion regulation and attachment security can mitigate the impact of psychosocial stressors on mood regulation and improve outcomes for individuals with bipolar disorder. Another central component of BD is the difficulties in emotion regulation. Attachment insecurity and trauma can disrupt this regulation, leading individuals to resort to substance use as a maladaptive coping mechanism. Therefore, therapeutic and psychopharmacological interventions that look at enhancing emotion regulation are crucial for reducing the risk of developing BD and concurrent addiction, as well as for assisting individuals in coping with challenging symptoms, processing traumatic experiences, and addressing the impacts of attachment-related difficulties. A comprehensive understanding of psychosocial developmental risk factors, including childhood trauma, attachment styles, and early substance use, is essential for effectively understanding, assessing, intervening, and managing bipolar disorder.

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